

GOMA: A PROGRAMME TO EMPOWER YOUTH THROUGH SCIENCE

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Good afternoon everyone, and welcome to Armamar.

My name is Cândida Sarabando, I am a Physics and Chemistry teacher at the Agrupamento de Escolas Gomes Teixeira and the coordinator of GOMA – the Gomes Teixeira Science Academy, our school's Science Club supported by the Portuguese Ciência Viva initiative.

GOMA was born in 2022, in response to a specific need: to strengthen our students' contact with hands-on experimental science. But it quickly became something greater. We realised that in a territory like ours, promoting science requires opening the school to the region, to the community, and to the future of our youth.

That is what we did: we built a multidisciplinary team of teachers from different areas and school levels, and we established partnerships with universities, scientific institutions, the municipality and even local businesses. We develop interdisciplinary projects aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. We explore themes such as biodiversity, sustainability, public health, but also scientific citizenship, equity and participation.

Our students are the first to be targeted, but our intervention plan also includes their families and the community in general. Our students are at the centre of our action — but they are not just recipients. They are facilitators, moderators, and science ambassadors. Many have already presented at national youth forums, led sessions of "Tapas de Ciência", or co-organised the European Researchers' Night in Armamar.

More than teaching science, we aim to develop key competences: critical thinking, communication, collaboration and creativity. We believe these skills are fundamental to our students' success — academically, personally, and professionally. And they are particularly relevant to empowering youth for their future employability — here, or anywhere.

GOMA was also the seed of ARMA-Sci – the Association for the Promotion of Armamar's Science Capital. A structure that was born out of the work initiated within the school, and that now allows science to reach even further in the territory, always with young people at the centre.

It is with great pride that I now pass the floor to Raquel Branquinho, president of ARMA-Sci, who will share more about the journey and impact of this association, which I am also proud to have co-founded.

Thank you.